

STRESS FIELDS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH MID-SURFACE DELAMINATION

N. J. Pagano

WL/MLBM

Materials Directorate

Wright Patterson Air Force Base, OH 45433-6533, USA

S. R. Soni

AdTech Systems Research, Inc.

1342 N. Fairfield Road

Beavercreek, OH 45432, USA

ABSTRACT

Composite laminates with different defects or stress raisers have been a subject of extensive investigations. Various authors have made different assumptions to arrive at approximate results. Pagano developed a model based upon Reissner's variational principle in 1978 and is used to solve the subject boundary value problem. The governing equations of equilibrium are obtained from extended Reissner's variational theorem for layered media. This paper deals with the (1) stress analysis of a laminate with free-free surface conditions and (2) stress analysis of a laminate with partial mid-surface delamination. Following the solution procedure described in papers [1, 2] for free-edge stress analysis, relations are obtained to conduct the stress analysis of a composite laminate with appropriate boundary conditions. Results are given for one example for each case. Where appropriate, a comparison with existing results has been made. It is evident from results that the present model can accurately predict stress fields at each location of the laminate including interlaminar stresses. The calculated stress components can be used in an appropriate failure theory to determine the propagation of the damage.

INTRODUCTION

The composite laminate in which an interlaminar crack is present in one or more interfaces has been the subject of extensive research in recent years. Delamination or transverse cracking is usually the first mode of failure to occur in a structural composite laminate. Under loading, damage growth is produced in the form of additional transverse cracks and/or delaminations which may or may not be precipitated by the existing transverse cracks. Such damage growth is the precursor to ultimate failure under static and fatigue loading conditions. Besides, in experimental measurements these cracks influence the resulting material property beyond the development of the first crack.

In this work, we study the response of a symmetric (or unsymmetric) laminate with its cross-section in the xz -plane under tensile loading applied at the end $y=\pm L/2$. Here we let z represent the direction normal to the plane of lamination. Solutions are based upon the local model [1,2] derived from Reissner's variational theorem [3]. In this model, field equations and boundary conditions are written for each layer so that realistic equilibrium relations can be satisfied. Loading applied by the testing machine is simulated via strain conditions.

The details of the solution that are of interest include the values of the interlaminar stresses, which govern the tendency to delaminate, the in-plane tensile stress distribution, which determines whether a transverse crack will occur, and the length of the boundary layer region in which highly intensified interlaminar stresses act. The effect of stacking sequence and the effect of the constraint by adjacent layers will also be addressed. Furthermore, the stress fields in the interface regions is of great interest.

Following the solution procedure described in papers by N.J. Pagano for uncracked laminates, relations are obtained to conduct the stress analysis of composite laminate with delamination under the influence of inplane strain boundary conditions. The model is general to consider any number of cracked/delaminated layers in general laminates. The current application is limited to laminates with free-free surface boundary conditions and partially delaminated laminates. For the latter case the solutions are developed considering two regions along the width of the laminate, one delaminated and the other undelaminated. Equilibrium equations are solved for each region and appropriate boundary conditions are applied for solving the boundary value problem. Two cases are considered for computation of results. One case demonstrates the solution for free-free surface boundary condition in (90/0)_i laminate and the second case illustrates single layer (90)_i solution with delaminated and undelaminated regions. The calculated stress components can be used in an appropriate failure theory to determine the development and propagation of the damage.

BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM

Figure 1 shows the laminate with coordinate axes, loading direction and sign conventions. The theory is developed for a general laminate with any ply angle and stacking sequence, and the load is represented as an applied strain ϵ along y-direction at the end $y=L/2$. On the basis of Reissner's variational theorem [3] and its extension to layered media [1], the governing equilibrium equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} + t_2 - t_1 &= 0 \\
 N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} + s_2 - s_1 &= 0 \\
 V_{x,x} + V_{y,y} + \frac{20M_z}{h^2} + p_1 - p_2 - \frac{h}{6}(t_{1,x} + t_{2,x} + s_{1,y} + s_{2,y}) &= 0 \\
 M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} - V_x + \frac{h}{2}(t_1 + t_2) &= 0 \\
 M_{xy,x} + M_{y,y} - V_y + \frac{h}{2}(s_1 + s_2) &= 0 \\
 N_z - \frac{(p_1 + p_2)h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{12}(t_{1,x} - t_{2,x} + s_{1,y} - s_{2,y}) &= 0 \\
 V_{x,x} + V_{y,y} + \frac{60M_z}{h^2} + 5(p_1 - p_2) - \frac{h}{2}(t_{1,x} + t_{2,x} + s_{1,y} + s_{2,y}) &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

and the constitutive relations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h\left(\frac{\bar{u}_{,x}}{2} - e_x\right) &= S_{11}N_x + S_{12}N_y + S_{13}N_z + S_{16}N_{xy} \\
 h\left(\frac{\bar{v}_{,y}}{2} - e_y\right) &= S_{12}N_x + S_{22}N_y + S_{23}N_z + S_{26}N_{xy} \\
 3w^* - he_z &= S_{13}N_x + S_{23}N_y + \frac{6}{5}S_{33}N_z + S_{36}N_{xy} - \frac{S_{33}h}{10}(p_1 + p_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$h \frac{\bar{u}_{,y} + \bar{v}_{,x}}{2} - e_{xy}) = S_{16}N_x + S_{26}N_y + S_{36}N_z + S_{66}N_{xy}$$

$$\frac{h^2}{4} u^*_{,x} = S_{11}M_x + S_{12}M_y + S_{13}M_z + S_{16}M_{xy} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{h^2}{4} v^*_{,y} = S_{12}M_x + S_{22}M_y + S_{23}M_z + S_{26}M_{xy}$$

$$\frac{5h}{4}(3\hat{w} - \bar{w}) = S_{13}M_x + S_{23}M_y + \frac{10}{7}S_{33}M_z + S_{36}M_{xy} + \frac{S_{33}h^2}{28}(p_1 - p_2)$$

$$\frac{h^2}{4}(u^*_{,y} + v^*_{,x}) = S_{16}M_x + S_{26}M_y + S_{36}M_z + S_{66}M_{xy}$$

$$\frac{3}{4}(\bar{w}_y - \hat{w}_y + \frac{4v^*}{h}) = \frac{6}{5h}(S_{44}V_y + S_{45}V_x) - \frac{S_{44}}{10}(s_1 + s_2) - \frac{S_{45}}{10}(t_1 + t_2)$$

$$\frac{3}{4}(\bar{w}_x - \hat{w}_x + \frac{4u^*}{h}) = \frac{6}{5h}(S_{45}V_y + S_{55}V_x) - \frac{S_{45}}{10}(s_1 + s_2) - \frac{S_{55}}{10}(t_1 + t_2)$$

The equilibrium equations (1) and the constitutive relations (2) must be satisfied in each layer. In the derivation of these relations, the following stress and stress resultant relations, valid in each layer of the laminate, have been used:

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_x = \frac{N_x}{h} + \frac{12M_x z}{h^3}$$

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_y = \frac{N_y}{h} + \frac{12M_y z}{h^3}$$

$$\sigma_6 = \tau_{xy} = \frac{N_{xy}}{h} + \frac{12M_{xy} z}{h^3}$$

$$\sigma_3 = \sigma_z = \frac{(p_1 + p_2)}{4} \left(\frac{12z^2}{h^2} - 1 \right) + \frac{(p_2 - p_1)}{4} \left(\frac{40z^3}{h^3} - \frac{6z}{h} \right) + \frac{3N_z}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) + \frac{15M_z}{h^2} \left(\frac{2z}{h} - \frac{8z^3}{h^3} \right)$$

$$\sigma_4 = \tau_{yz} = \frac{z}{h}(s_2 - s_1) + \frac{(s_1 + s_2)}{4} \left(\frac{12z^2}{h^2} - 1 \right) + \frac{3V_y}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_5 = \tau_{xz} = \frac{z}{h}(t_2 - t_1) + \frac{(t_1 + t_2)}{4} \left(\frac{12z^2}{h^2} - 1 \right) + \frac{3V_x}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right)$$

where the shear resultants V_x , V_y and the function N_z , M_z given by

$$(N_z, M_z) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_z(1, z) dz$$

and N_x , ..., M_{xy} are function of x and y . These functions represent force and moment resultants arising in the laminated theory. The interlaminar stress components σ_z , τ_{xz} , τ_{yz} at the top of the layer are denoted by p_2 , t_2 , and s_2 , respectively, while the corresponding stress components at the bottom of the layer are designated by p_1 , t_1 , and s_1 . The parameter h represents the layer thickness. It is appropriate to mention that the introduction of p_i , t_i , and s_i , ($i=1,2$) helps the accurate and efficient computation of interlaminar stresses in the laminate. The following definitions have been used in this investigation:

$$(\bar{f}, \hat{f}^*, \hat{f}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} f(1, \frac{2z}{h}, \frac{4z^2}{h^2}) \frac{2dz}{h} \quad (4)$$

where f can be any one of the displacement components u, v and w .
The interface continuity conditions are given by:

Interface Conditions:

a) Continuity ($k = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$)

$$\begin{aligned} t_2^{(k)} &= t_1^{(k+1)}, & s_2^{(k)} &= s_1^{(k+1)}, & p_2^{(k)} &= p_1^{(k+1)} \\ \beta_4^{(k)} - S_{44}^{(k)} T_4^{(k)} - S_{45}^{(k)} T_5^{(k)} + \alpha_4^{(k+1)} - S_{44}^{(k+1)} Q_4^{(k+1)} - S_{45}^{(k+1)} Q_5^{(k+1)} &= 0 \\ \beta_5^{(k)} - S_{45}^{(k)} T_4^{(k)} - S_{55}^{(k)} T_5^{(k)} + \alpha_5^{(k+1)} - S_{45}^{(k+1)} Q_4^{(k+1)} - S_{55}^{(k+1)} Q_5^{(k+1)} &= 0 \\ \gamma_2^{(k)} - S_{33}^{(k)} R_2^{(k)} + \gamma_1^{(k+1)} - S_{33}^{(k+1)} R_1^{(k+1)} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

b) Prescribed Tractions and/or Displacements ($k = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$)

$$\begin{aligned} t_2^{(k)} &= \tilde{t}_2^{(k)} \quad \text{or} \quad \beta_5^{(k)} - S_{45}^{(k)} T_4^{(k)} - S_{55}^{(k)} T_5^{(k)} = -\tilde{u}_2^{(k)} \\ s_2^{(k)} &= \tilde{s}_2^{(k)} \quad \text{or} \quad \beta_4^{(k)} - S_{44}^{(k)} T_4^{(k)} - S_{45}^{(k)} T_5^{(k)} = -\tilde{v}_2^{(k)} \\ p_2^{(k)} &= \tilde{p}_2^{(k)} \quad \text{or} \quad \gamma_2^{(k)} - S_{33}^{(k)} R_2^{(k)} = -\tilde{w}_2^{(k)} \\ t_1^{(k+1)} &= \tilde{t}_1^{(k+1)} \quad \text{or} \quad \alpha_5^{(k+1)} - S_{45}^{(k+1)} Q_4^{(k+1)} - S_{55}^{(k+1)} Q_5^{(k+1)} = \tilde{u}_1^{(k+1)} \\ s_1^{(k+1)} &= \tilde{s}_1^{(k+1)} \quad \text{or} \quad \alpha_4^{(k+1)} - S_{44}^{(k+1)} Q_4^{(k+1)} - S_{45}^{(k+1)} Q_5^{(k+1)} = \tilde{v}_1^{(k+1)} \\ p_1^{(k+1)} &= \tilde{p}_1^{(k+1)} \quad \text{or} \quad \gamma_1^{(k+1)} - S_{33}^{(k+1)} R_1^{(k+1)} = \tilde{w}_1^{(k+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Also the following contractions are introduced in equations (5) and (6):

$$\begin{aligned} Q_4 &= \frac{(4s_1 - s_2)h}{30} - \frac{V_y}{10}, & Q_5 &= \frac{(4t_1 - t_2)h}{30} - \frac{V_x}{10} \\ T_4 &= \frac{(4s_2 - s_1)h}{30} - \frac{V_y}{10}, & T_5 &= \frac{(4t_2 - t_1)h}{30} - \frac{V_x}{10} \\ R_1 &= \frac{(6p_1 + p_2)h^2 - 7N_z h + 30M_z}{70h}, & R_2 &= \frac{(6p_2 + p_1)h^2 - 7N_z h - 30M_z}{70h} \end{aligned} \quad (6a)$$

$$\begin{cases} \beta_4 \\ \alpha_4 \end{cases} = \frac{3}{8}h\hat{w}_{,y} - \frac{h}{8}\bar{w}_{,y} - \frac{3}{2}v^* \pm \left(\frac{h}{4}w^*_{,y} - \frac{\bar{v}}{2}\right)$$

$$\begin{cases} \beta_5 \\ \alpha_5 \end{cases} = \frac{3}{8}h\hat{w}_{,x} - \frac{h}{8}\bar{w}_{,x} - \frac{3}{2}u^* \pm \left(\frac{h}{4}w^*_{,x} - \frac{\bar{u}}{2}\right)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1 \\ \gamma_2 \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{3}{2}w^* \pm \frac{3}{4}(5\widehat{w} - \bar{w})$$

SOLUTION TECHNIQUE

We consider a laminate in which each layer is reinforced by a system of parallel fibers in the xy-plane (Fig. 1). The body is subjected to forces applied only on the ends such that a constant axial strain ϵ is imposed. Each layer is also under the influence of expansional strain ϵ_i ($i = 1,2,3,6$) which we assume are constants. We also assume perfect bonding between adjacent layers. Hence, the stress field in this class of problems is a function of x and z alone. The laminate consists of N layers which are identified by the index k ($k = 1,2,\dots,N$). As in [1], we shall drop the index k except when it is needed for clarity.

The deformation measures ϵ_i , κ_β , and expansional deformations α_β are defined in [1,2]. Since the stresses in the present class of boundary value problems depend only on x and z , it follows that the force and moment resultants and the interlaminar stresses will depend only on x . Hence, the deformation measures are functions of x alone and by use of strain displacement relations, it can be shown that the most general form of the weighted displacements is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{u} &= U(x) - \frac{c_1}{2}y^2 + c_3y, \\ \bar{v} &= V(x) + c_1xy + c_2y \\ h\bar{w} &= W(x) - 6c_3xy + 3c_4y - 3c_6y^2 \\ u^* &= \phi(x) + c_5y \\ v^* &= \Omega(x) + c_6y \\ w^* &= \phi(x) \\ h\widehat{w} &= \chi(x) - 2c_5xy + c_4y - c_6y^2 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where U through χ are arbitrary functions of x and c_1 through c_6 are constants. We should recall that deformation measures, equilibrium equations and weighted displacements must be written for each layer. We now substitute eqs. (7) into (2), and then into the equilibrium equations, (1), in which the y dependence is dropped to establish seven equilibrium equations in terms of weighted displacement parameters of equations (7). The resulting equations are valid within each layer. The remaining field equations and the interface continuity conditions, are obtained by substituting (7) into (5).

Figure 1a. Laminate with free-free surface, y-axis normal to plane of paper with applied strain ϵ .

Figure 1b. Laminate with delaminated and undelaminated region

TRACTION BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Figure 1a shows the laminate with both top and bottom surfaces traction free and Figure 1b shows a laminate with delaminated surfaces at $0 \leq x \leq a$ and un-delaminated surface at $a \leq x \leq l$. Incorporating the traction-free conditions on the upper surface, our boundary conditions on the upper and lower surfaces for both cases are given below:

(1) Delaminated Region:

$$\tilde{w}^{(1)} = t_1^{(1)} = s_1^{(1)} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$t_2^{(N)} = s_2^{(N)} = p_2^{(N)} = 0$$

(2) Undelaminated Region:

$$p_1^{(1)} = t_1^{(1)} = s_1^{(1)} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$t_2^{(N)} = s_2^{(N)} = p_2^{(N)} = 0$$

The substitution of equations (7) in stress displacement relations (2) and their subsequent use in equations (1) lead to a set of equilibrium equations for each layer. These combined with interfacial continuity conditions provide us required number of equations. These equations must be satisfied for all values of x . It follows that

$$c_4^{(k)} = c_5^{(k)} = c_6^{(k)} = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (10)$$

and

$$c_1^{(k+1)} = c_1^{(k)}, \quad c_2^{(k+1)} = c_2^{(k)}, \quad c_3^{(k+1)} = c_3^{(k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad (11)$$

so that c_1 , c_2 and c_3 are the same for every layer.

EDGE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

We now turn our attention to the edge boundary conditions. Because only edge tractions are imposed in the present class of boundary value problems, the parameters N_x , N_{xy} , V_x , M_x , M_{xy} , t_1 and t_2 for each layer on $x=-b$ and b are prescribed. However, all these functions cannot be independently prescribed because of the consequences of interface continuity and global equilibrium of the entire laminate.

Free-Free Surface Case

The edge boundary conditions for free-free surface case may be expressed as

$$N_x^{(k)}(\pm b) = N_{xy}^{(k)}(\pm b) = M_x^{(k)}(\pm b) = M_{xy}^{(k)}(\pm b) = V_x^{(k)}(\pm b) = t_2^{(k)}(\pm b) = 0 \quad (k=1, 2, \dots, N-1)$$

$$N_x^{(k)}(-b) = N_{xy}^{(k)}(-b) = M_x^{(k)}(-b) = M_{xy}^{(k)}(-b) = 0 \quad (k=N) \quad (12)$$

$$U^{*(k)}(-b) = V^{*(k)}(-b) = \overline{W}^{(k)}(-b) = 0 \quad (k=N)$$

Delaminated and Undelaminated Regions case

The edge boundary conditions for single layer with delaminated and undelaminated regions case are:

$$N_x^{(k)}(l) = M_x^{(k)}(l) = V_x(l) = 0, \quad N_x(0) = M_x(0) = V_x(0),$$

$$N_x(a)|_{p_1=0} = N_x(a)|_{p_1 \neq 0}, \quad V_x(a)|_{p_1=0} = V_x(a)|_{p_1 \neq 0}$$

$$\overline{u}_{p_1=0} = \overline{u}_{p_1 \neq 0}, \quad w_{p_1=0}^* = w_{p_1 \neq 0}^*, \quad u_{p_1=0}^* = u_{p_1 \neq 0}^*, \quad \widehat{w}_{p_1=0} = \widehat{w}_{p_1 \neq 0}, \quad \overline{w}_{p_1=0} = \overline{w}_{p_1 \neq 0}$$

The general solution for each dependent variable consists of the sum of two parts: (i) a complementary solution defined by the homogeneous form and, (ii) a particular solution. Because of laminate Poisson's ratio, we consider $2c_2 = \epsilon$, $c_1 = c_3 = 0$. Since the field equations are linear differential equations with constant coefficients, the complementary solution (subscript H) for each dependent variable consists of a series of terms of the form

$$f_H^{(k)} = F^{(k)} e^{\lambda y} \quad (13)$$

where $f^{(k)}$ stands for any of the dependent variables and $F^{(k)}$ are constants. The detailed solution procedure as given in reference [2] provides required parameters of interest.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

T300/5208 material has been taken as a representative material for the computation of results for illustrative examples of this problem. The following values of the engineering constants of the material have been used:

$$E_{11} = 126.2 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{12} = 5.52 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.3$$

$$E_{22} = 10.0 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{13} = 5.52 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{13} = 0.3$$

$$E_{33} = 10.0 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{23} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.52$$

where E, G and ν stand for Young's modulus, Shear modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. The subscripts denote the corresponding directions, where 1,2,3 stand for x, y, z, respectively, and ij is the Poisson's ratio measuring strain in the j direction caused by uniaxial stress σ_i .

Stress components σ_x , σ_z , τ_{xz} , and σ_z at the midsurface and the (0/90) interface in the case of (0/90)₁ laminate have been computed for a given inplane axial strain ($\epsilon_x = 0.1E-4$). These stress components calculated along the width of the laminate are presented in Table 1. The results are computed by considering each layer separately. The accuracy of results may improve if each layer is subdivided into number of layers.

Stress components σ_x , σ_z , τ_{xz} , and σ_z at z=0 surface at three locations of the laminate (90)_s with delaminated and undelaminated surfaces have been computed for a given inplane axial strain ($\epsilon_x = 0.1E-4$). These stress components calculated along the width of the laminate are presented

in Table 2. In this case also, the results are computed using single layer solution. Subdivision of layers may give better accuracy.

The results of table 1 show certain inaccuracy because σ_z at the lower surface of second layer should be zero. The work is in progress to check the influence of different parameters on response characteristics of the laminate.

FUTURE WORK

The scope of future work is extending the solution for including the delamination in laminates consisting of 0 and 90 layers. This work will incorporate the solutions developed for the above mentioned illustrative cases.

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Table 1. Stress components (Pa) at Free-Edge.

Stress Components	Layer No.1 (0 degree)		Layer No. 2 (90 degree)	
	Surface		Surface	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
σ_z	-8.22E+3	0.00E+0	-3.021E+4	-8.22E+3
τ_{yz}	-1.12E+4	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	-1.11E+4
σ_x	6.43E+4	2.92E+4	7.83E+4	-5.10E+4
σ_y	1.28E+6	1.27E+3	9.78E+4	8.17E+4

Table 2. Stress components (Pa) at different locations

Stress Components	x/b=0		x/b= 0.5		x/b= 1	
	Surface		Surface		Surface	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
σ_z	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	2.482E+3	0.00E+0	4.619E+3	0.00E+0
σ_x	-1.26E+4	1.26E+4	-9.92E+4	9.92E+4	-1.45E+5	1.86E+5
σ_y	1.20E+6	1.33E+6	1.17E+6	1.35E+6	1.20E+6	1.43E+6